

DEVELOPMENT OF ARAMID MULTI-LAYER FABRICS FOR CUT RESISANT TEXTILES

G. Hoffmann¹, P. Offermann¹, Y. Dietzel²

¹ *Technische Universität Dresden, Institut für Textil- und Bekleidungstechnik
D-01062 Dresden, Germany*

² *Sächsisches Textilforschungsinstitut e. V.
Postfach 13 25, D-09072 Chemnitz, Germany*

SUMMARY: In consequence of growing drug-related crime or unintentional destruction by more or less sharp edged objects, textiles are increasingly demanded from the consumers which show an additional protection against vandalism. On basis of different research projects, a multi-layer woven fabric made of Aramid yarns with a mass per unit area of 1000 - 1600 g/m² can be presented. The structure consists of two woven layers, the back and face cloth. The reinforcing threads of Aramid are inserted between the layers. The mechanical cutting tests result in an average cutting strength of 130 N and a maximum cutting strength of approx. 170 N. The testing of the cut resistance was based on the method developed by the Institute of Textile- and Clothing Technology. Cut resistant fabrics are necessary for convertible top materials, tarpaulins seats for the local public transport and long-distance traffic or transport bags.

KEYWORDS: woven fabric, Aramid, cut resistant fabric, double layer fabric

INTRODUCTION

In consequence of growing drug-related crime or unintentional destruction by more or less sharp edged objects, textiles are increasingly demanded from the consumers which show an additional protection against vandalism under perpetuation of existing high functional demands since the beginning of the nineties of the 20th Century. Examples are convertible top materials, tarpaulins seats for the local public transport and long-distance traffic or transport bags. Cut resistant products are already offered by different manufacturers. As reinforcing threads, materials with a high tensile strength are preferentially used e. g. steel wire, Aramid or hybrid yarns. At present cut resistant textiles with integrated steel wire show an average cutting strength of 80 - 230 N with a mass per unit area of 800 - 2000 g/m. Steel wire as a reinforcing material has different disadvantages like a bad workability during the manufacturing of the products, an insufficient adaptation to the product form due to the high flexural stiffness as well as a possible risk of injury in broken and outstanding wire ends. Certainly, Aramid can be processed easier, but it shows a lower cutting strength compared to steel wire which is compensated in practice by the application of a large quantity of Aramid. The area of conflict between the function of protection and the handling of these materials requires specific knowledge in terms of the mode of operation of cut resistant textiles as well as the determination of cut resistance, but also about the selection of suitable textile manufacturing processes for the fabric production and ready-made manufacturing. As a result of these re-

search projects it was found out that the weaving technology is the most suitable process for producing textiles with a high cutting strength [2].

CUT RESISTANT YARN

A special yarn material, which has high tensile strength and low stiffness, is necessary to develop a cut resistant fabric. Shearing resistance and the hardness of the yarn are also of particular importance. In fact all polymer yarns offer by increasing tensile strength and hardness a falling shearing resistance. Because of their inadequate shearing strength, glass and carbon yarns are totally unsuitable. Fig. 1 shows the correlation between tensile strength and cutting force of different single threads.

stainless steel (245,0 tex), Aramid (336,0 tex), PES-Monofil., single (98,2 tex), PES-Monofil., double (196,4 tex), AR-TPU (445,0 tex)

Fig. 1: Correlation between tensile strength and cutting force of single threads[1]

Aramid gives the highest cutting strength and it looks like the Aramid yarn is the best. If allowed stainless steel have the 6-fold density of Aramid and diameter is very low, stainless steel is the better material for some applications. A fabric with a very low stiffness is searched in this project and so Aramid yarn is selected.

FABRIC CONSTRUCTION

Different research projects about the analysis of cutting behavior of non-reinforced and reinforced textile structures proved that the weaving technologies are the most suitable processes for producing textiles with a high cutting strength. The properties of cut resistant woven fabrics depend predominantly on the choice of suitable reinforcing materials and their kind of integration into the surface. The effectiveness of the reinforcing materials regarding to the cutting strength is primarily determined by the selection of suitable thread materials, the yarn count, weft and warp density as well as the kind of their integration into the layers. For the fabric construction it has to be considered the following. There is a linear correlation between the maximum tensile strength of the reinforcing material and the cutting force of a single thread. Coarse yarn counts result in a higher cut resistance.

To develop a cut resistant fabric the cut resistant yarn must be inserted to the woven fabric. In the initial point the fundamental principles of the construction of cut resistant fabrics were tested. The main parameters are the binding point distance and the distance between the reinforcing threads. There was detected an optimum for the binding point distance considering the properties of the reinforced yarn. The cutting force increases, while the distance between the reinforcing yarns is reduced. The effective local yarn accumulations stop the knife hard [1]. This effect is called the cable effect, which has essential yarn floats inside the fabric.

To obtain high cut resistance, local yarn accumulations (cable effect) in warp and weft directions, which are inserted between the face and back cloth of a double layer fabric, are necessary. These can be made by yarn floats with a defined length depending on the selection of reinforcing material; suitable floating lengths for Aramid are between 30 and 60 mm. Aramid presents a low linear increase of the cutting force by a simultaneously increase of the floating length. The reinforcing yarns are integrated displaced into the fabric in order to avoid weak points as a result of missing yarn floats. The cut resistance increases with an increase of the warp and weft density of the reinforcing threads. The cut resistance is also determined by the yarn thickness of the reinforcing material. Fig. 2 gives a sample of cut resistant woven Aramid fabric and its warp and weft sections.

Fig.2: cut resistant woven Aramid fabric represented in warp and weft section [2]

The face and back cloths of the woven fabric should be made of a high-tensile material, which avoids the phenomenon that the integrated reinforcing threads are pulled out during the cutting process. The face and back sides of the fabric are to be patterned smooth and close so that an additional coating (if necessary) is possible. A lightweight coating with a very thin, ductile foil can additionally increase the cutting strength and makes it more difficult for the penetration of the cutting tool [3].

TESTING OF THE CUT RESISTANCE MECANISM

The testing of the cut resistance is based on the method developed by the Institute of Textile and Clothing Technology. The principle of testing; a fabric (300 mm x 500 mm) is stretched with a predetermined tension, moved on a carriage with a predetermined speed and made to cut with a knife having defined properties. For measuring the cutting force, a knife with a slope of 60° is pierced around 10 – 25 mm inside the sample and the force required to cut the sample is determined through the steel cable attached to the carriage. The cutting speed is generally fixed at 1 mm/s. From the force measured, the arithmetic mean and the maximum force in a particular interval of the force curve are determined. With this test method the smallest applied cutting force can be determined. All cutting forces are still higher in the practice.

- λ – Angle between the cutter and the cut resistant fabric
- p – Pressure on the cut resistant fabric
- t – Depth of the cut-in
- v – Speed of the cutter

Fig. 3: Principle cut resistance testing

Fig. 4: Sample result of testing the cut resistance

Fig. 4 shows a sample of a result of testing the cut resistance. The curve progression provides the behaviour of the fabric under the cutting mechanism. The test evaluates the maximum cutting force, the corresponding cutting distance and the average of local maxima of the cutting force.

RESULTS

On basis of different research projects, a multi-layer woven fabric made of Aramid with a mass per unit area of 1000 - 1600 g/m² is presented. This fabric matches the requirements for a high cut-resistant fabric. The structure consists of two woven layers, the back and face cloth. The reinforcing threads of Aramid, 1680 dtex, are inserted between the layers of the fabric in weft and warp direction. The reinforcing threads are alternately integrated into the face and back cloth and connect the both layers. The mechanical cutting tests result in an average cutting strength of 130 N and a maximum cutting strength of approx. 170 N. The cutting of the woven fabric with a ceramic-coated Aramid shear is hardly possible. At least 20 minutes is

necessary for a cutting length of approx. 5 cm. This effect will be increased if the woven fabric is loosely fixed and the possibility for the formation of wrinkles is available. Other important product attributes are a good drape ability and ready-made. This cut resistant fabric can be cut e. g. by means of an ultrasonic-cutter.

SUMMARY

Different woven fabrics with high cut resistances could be developed. Through the various applications for cut resistant textiles, a first trial product sample for a cut resistant convertible top is developed. The textile volume in the convertible top consists of the main components headliner, padding and convertible top cover. An evaluation of the product requirements of the convertible top showed that a technological intervention in the top cover drastically reduces its functional properties. But the multi-layer design of a convertible top permits a separately manufactured cut resistant fabric optionally placed in the convertible top between the top cover and the padding. For economic reason the optimum must be found between the cutting force and the required area weight of the reinforced structures.

REFERENCES

1. Finkelmeyer, S.: Grundlagen zur Konstruktion textiler Flächengebilde mit erhöhter Schneidresistenz für den Objektschutz. *Dissertation, 2001. – Technische Universität Dresden*
2. Dietzel, Y.: Schnittmechanische Untersuchungen zur bindungstechnischen Konstruktion von schnittfesten Geweben für Bezugstoffe. *Institut für Textil- und Bekleidungstechnik, AiF-Abschlußbericht 12459 B / 5, 2002*
3. Dietzel, Y.; Offermann, P.; Hoffmann, G.; Wehlmann, J.: New Solutions for coated textiles with cutting strengths without the application of stainless steel wire. *Techtextil Symposium, Frankfurt, 07.-10.04.2003*